

Titanium (IV) Complexes with the Schiff Bases Derived from the Condensation of Salicylaldehyde or Orthohydroxyacetophenone with n-Hydroxyalkylamines

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The reactions of titanium isopropoxide with a few tridentate Schiff bases, derived by the condensation of salicylaldehyde or orthohydroxyacetophenone with n-hydroxyalkylamines, in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios have been investigated and new derivatives of the type $Ti(OPr^i)_2(SB)$ and $Ti(SB)_2$ have been isolated (where—SB—represents the anion of the Schiff base). The replacement reactions of di-isopropoxy derivatives with other alcohols, phenol, salicyl-aldehyde, 2-hydroxyethylamine and 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol have also been carried out. The I.R. spectral studies of a few representative derivatives have been made and their molecular weights determined ebullioscopically in benzene. In some of these derivatives the possibility of penta-coordinated titanium has been indicated.

In the present paper, the reactions of titanium isopropoxide with a few tridentate Schiff bases have been described. These reactions in the molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 may be represented by the following equations :

Where SBH_2 can be either :

- (i) Salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine;
- (ii) Orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxyethylimine;
- or (iii) Orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-n-propylimine.

and (SB) represents the anion of the Schiff bases.

The experimental technique was the same as described earlier¹. All the resulting derivatives are light or dark yellow solids (Table I) and can be crystallized from benzene or isopropanol.

To show the labile nature of isopropoxy groups, several interchange reactions of di-isopropoxy titanium (IV) Schiff base derivatives with other alcohols and phenol (Table II) and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyethylamine and 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol (Table III) have

1. P. Prashar and J. P. Tandon, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1967, 13, 541.

TABLE I
Reactions of Titanium Isopropoxide with Schiff Bases in Benzene

Reactants	Molar Ratio	State, yield and molecular formula	Alcohol in azeotrope (g)		Analysis		Molecular Weight	Remarks			
			Found	Calc.	% of Metal Found	% of Nitrogen Calc.					
Ti(OPr) ⁴ (2.58 g) + Salicylidene-2-hydroxy- n-propylamine (1.64 g)	1 : 1	Foamy yellow solid (3.12 g) Ti(OPr) ³ ₂ (SB)	1.04	1.09	13.91	13.95	3.98	4.08	682	343	Crystallizable from isopropanol. On heating yellow colour changed to slightly dark yellow and finally changed into golden yellow mass at about 189-191°C.
Ti(OPr) ⁴ (1.62 g) + Salicylidene-2-hydroxy- n-propylamine (2.05 g)	1 : 2	Yellow solid (2.34 g). Ti(SB) ₂	1.34	1.36	12.03	11.91	6.78	6.96	437	402	Crystallizable from isopropanol, shining crystals. On heating, softening occurred at about 186-188°C and changed into red viscous mass at about 190-192°C.
Ti(OPr) ⁴ (3.23 g) + Orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-ethylamine (2.04 g).	1 : 1	Yellow solid, (3.98 g) Ti(OPr) ³ ₂ (SB)	1.36	1.36	14.31	13.95	4.04	4.08	363	343	Crystallizable from isopropanol and benzene. On heating softening took place at about 132-135°C and slowly decomposed into brown black mass at about 220°C.
Ti(OPr) ⁴ (2.51 g) + Orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-ethylamine (3.17 g)	1 : 2	Pale yellow solid (3.47 g) Ti(SB) ₂ .	2.11	2.12	11.98	11.91	6.85	6.96	408	402	Crystallizable from benzene. On heating shining crystals changed into dull powder at about 90-100°C and decomposed into a red-brown liquid at about 275°C.

TABLE I—Contd.

Reactants	Molar Ratio	State, yield and molecular formula	Alcohol in azeotrope (g)		Analysis				Molecular Weight	Remarks		
			Found	Calc.	% of Metal	% of Nitrogen	Found	Calc.			Found	Calc.
Ti(OPr) ⁴ ₄ (3.72 g) + Orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-n-propylimine (2.53 g)	1 : 1	Yellowish solid (4.64 g) Ti(OPr ⁴) ₂ (SB)	1.53	1.57	13.14	13.41	3.41	3.95	3.92	378	357	Crystallizable from isopropanol. On heating the colour changed slowly from pale yellow to dark yellow and finally in- to reddish yellow.
Ti(OPr) ⁴ ₄ (1.65 g) + Orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-n-propylimine (2.24 g)	1 : 2	Dirty yellowish solid (2.51 g) Ti(SB) ₂	1.35	1.39	11.42	11.13	6.73	6.51	6.51	Crystallizable from isopropanol. On heating slowly changed in colour and finally into black mass at about 250°C.

SB represents the anion of the corresponding Schiff bases.

been carried out. These reactions, gave new derivatives in almost quantitative yields and can be represented as follows :

Where SB = anion of Schiff bases and
R & R' = alkyl groups of alcohols & glycols
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The isopropoxyphenoxy titanium (IV) salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine has also been isolated by the reaction of phenol with diisopropoxy titanium (IV) salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

The molecular weights of almost all the derivatives soluble in benzene have been determined. Diisopropoxy (Fig. I), diethoxy (Fig. II), dimethoxy (Fig. III) and isopropoxyphenoxy (Fig. IV), titanium (IV) derivatives of salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine are all dimers in boiling benzene. In these compounds dimerization through isopropoxy bridges helps the central titanium atom to attain its stable hexacoordination. Other derivatives of salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine, such as, ditert-butoxy titanium (IV) (Fig. V) and diphenoxy titanium (IV) (Fig. VI) are monomers, as steric effect of the bulky groups inhibits the association. Their tentative structures can be indicated by the following figures :

(Figs. I- IV)

Fig. (I), R = R' = Pr^t (II) R = R' = Et
(III), R = R' = Me & (IV) R = C₆H₅, R' = Pr^t

In Figs (V) R = H, R₁ = CH₃, R' = Et^t
 (VI) R = H, R₁ = CH₃, R' = C₆H₅
 (VII) R = CH₃, R₁ = H, R' = Et^t
 (VIII) R = CH₃, R₁ = CH₃, R' = Pr^t
 (IX) R = CH₃, R₁ = H, R' = C₆H₅
 and (X) R = CH₃, R₁ = CH₃, R' = C₆H₅

The monomeric diisopropoxy and diphenoxy titanium (IV) Schiff base derivatives of orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxyethylamine [Figs. (VII) and (IX) respectively] and orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-n-propylimine Fig. (VIII) and (X) respectively are probably examples of pentacoordinated titanium. However, the corresponding ethoxy and methoxy derivatives tend to polymerize as shown by their slightly higher degree of molecular association (Table II). Other derivatives obtained from the interchange reactions, are also monomers.

TABLE-II

Interchange Reactions of Diisopropoxy Titanium (IV) Schiff Base Complexes with Alcohols and Phenols

Product, yield and state	Amount of alcohol in azeotrope in (g)		Analysis				Molecular weight	
	Found	Calc.	% of Metal		% of Nitrogen		Found	Calc.
Ti(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ (OPr ^t) ₂ (SB) Yellowish red foamy solid.	0.276	0.278	12.95	12.70	3.55	3.71	684	377
Ti(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ (SB) Red Solid.	0.604	0.606	11.68	11.65	3.39	3.40	452	411
Ti(OBu ^t) ₂ (SB) Yellow semi-solid.	0.647	0.631	13.26	12.90	3.59	3.77	416	371
Ti(OEt) ₂ (SB) Reddish yellow foamy solid.	15.45	15.19	4.39	4.44	745	315
Ti(OMe) ₂ (SB) Foamy yellow solid.	16.56	16.68	4.62	4.87	586	287
Ti(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ (S ¹ B ¹)	0.439	0.457	11.42	11.65	3.44	3.40	461	411
Ti(OEt) ₂ (S ¹ B ¹) Yellow solid.	15.22	15.19	4.35	4.42	552	315
Ti(OMe) ₂ (S ¹ B ¹) Yellow solid.	16.63	16.68	4.70	4.87	490	287
Ti(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ (S ₁ B ₁) Red solid.	0.440	0.458	11.39	11.24	3.20	3.29
Ti(OEt) ₂ (S ₁ B ₁) Yellow solid.	14.40	14.55	4.19	4.25	519	329
Ti(OMe) ₂ (S ₁ B ₁) Yellow solid.	16.08	15.91	4.59	4.64	528	301

where SB = anion of salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine.

S¹B¹ = anion of orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxyethylamine

S₁B₁ = anion of orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-n-propylimine

Titanium (IV)-bis-salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine (Fig. XI) and titanium (IV)-bis-orthohydroxy-2-hydroxyethylimine (Fig. XII) are also monomers in boiling benzene and their tentative structures may be indicated as follows :

In Figs (XI) $R = H$ & $R_1 = CH_3$
 & (XII) $R = CH_3$ & $R_1 = H$

Infra-red measurements : Infra-red spectra of the Schiff bases (I, II and III) and their corresponding titanium (IV) complexes were studied as Nujol mulls by Perkin-Elmer Infracord model 337 between 4000–400 cm^{-1} region using KBr optics.

A few characteristic absorption bands with tentative assignments are as follows :

3400 cm^{-1} –3100 cm^{-1} region : All the three Schiff bases (I, II and III) showed bands at 3380 (sb), 3140 (mb) and 3127 (s) cm^{-1} respectively, which may be tentatively assigned to -OH or NH- stretching modes.

1650-1600 cm^{-1} region : The Schiff base (I) showed the characteristic -C = N- band at 1625 (vs) cm^{-1} which shifts to 1640 cm^{-1} in the titanium complexes. In the remaining Schiff bases (II and III) and their complexes, this remains unaltered at 1601 (vs) cm^{-1} .

640-600 cm^{-1} region : The titanium (IV) complexes of Schiff base (I) gave only one strong absorption band at 625 (vs) cm^{-1} whereas in similar derivatives of other Schiff bases (II and III) absorption bands at 620 (vs) and 630 (m) cm^{-1} were observed.

From the above observations, it appears that in these derivatives the coordination takes place through the oxygen of the alcoholic and phenolic groups as it is supported by :

- (i) The disappearance of the bands in the 3400-3100 cm^{-1} region in the titanium (IV) complexes.
- (ii) The appearance of strong bands in the region of 620-630 cm^{-1} in titanium (IV) complexes and which can be assigned to Ti-O band similar to Ti-O bond in titanium alkoxides³.

Abbreviations : vs = very strong, m = medium, b = broad, s = strong.

2. P. Prashar and J. P. Tandon, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1968, **15**, 219.

3. G.G. Barraclough, D. C. Bradley, J. Lewis, and I. M. Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2601.

The $\text{-C}=\text{N-}$ stretch of the Schiff base is very little affected on coordination with the metal ion⁴. In the complexes of Schiff bases (II) and (III) it remains almost unchanged at 1601 cm^{-1} . However, in the derivatives of Schiff base (I) it appears at 1640 cm^{-1} in place of 1625 cm^{-1} in the Schiff base.

TABLE-III

Reactions of Diisopropoxytitanium (IV) Schiff base complexes with Bidentate Ligands

Product, yield and state	Amount of alcohol in the azeotrope, in (g)		Analysis				Molecular Weight	
	Found	Calc.	% of Titanium		% of Nitrogen		Found	Calc.
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
Ti(2-Methyl-2,4-pentanediol) (SB) Foamy yellow solid.	0.617	0.618	14.35	14.04	3.94	4.10	456	341
Ti(Salicylaldehyde) ₂ (SB) Reddish foamy solid.	1.009	1.090	10.42	10.25	2.90	2.99	434	467
Ti(2-hydroxyethylamine) ₂ (SB) Yellow foamy solid.	0.757	0.772	13.82	13.89	12.04	12.17	466	345
Ti(2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol) (S ¹ B ¹) Yellow solid.	1.068	1.070	14.37	14.04	4.10	4.10	411	341
Ti(Salicylaldehyde) ₂ (S ¹ B ¹) Red foamy solid.	0.848	0.883	9.95	10.25	2.97	2.99	447	467
Ti(2-hydroxyethylamine) ₂ (S ¹ B ¹) Yellow foamy solid.	0.843	0.870	13.53	13.89	11.93	12.17	431	345
Ti(2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol) (S ₁ B ₁) Yellow solid.	0.977	1.004	13.86	13.49	3.80	3.94	548	355
Ti(Salicylaldehyde) ₂ (S ₁ B ₁) Red foamy solid.	0.787	0.811	10.38	9.95	2.83	2.90	457	481
Ti(2-hydroxyethylamine) ₂ (S ₁ B ₁) Yellow foamy solid.	0.886	0.891	13.83	13.33	11.68	11.70	436	359

SB represents the anion of the corresponding Schiff base.

EXPERIMENTAL

Titanium isopropoxide was prepared by the ammonia method⁵. Salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyethylamine and 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol were all distilled before use. Salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine was prepared as described earlier². Similarly, other Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of orthohydroxyacetophenone with 2-hydroxyethylimine or 2-hydroxy-n-propylimine. Both orthohydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxyethylimine and

4. B. D. Sarma and J. C. Bailar, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5476.

5. D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2027.

ortho-hydroxy-acetophenone-2-hydroxy-n-propylimine are distillable yellow solids. *Ortho-hydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxyethylimine* : Found : C, 67.20; H, 7.91; N, 7.73%, Calc., C, 66.96; H, 7.31; N, 7.81%; m.p. 95-96°; b.p. 160°/0.6 mm or 153-159°/0.3-0.4 mm. *Ortho-hydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-n-propylimine* : Found : C, 68.98; H, 8.35; N, 7.15%; Calc.: C, 68.42; H, 7.83; N, 7.24%, m.p. 90-92°; b.p. 161°/1 mm or 144-145°/0.2-0.3 mm.

Titanium was determined by the dioxide method and the alcohol oxidimetrically⁶. Nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl method.

Reactions

Reactions of the Schiff bases with titanium isopropoxide in ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : On mixing Schiff bases with titanium isopropoxide in the molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 in dry benzene, slight heat was produced. The refluxing of reaction mixtures was carried out under a fractionation column and the benzene-isopropanol azeotrope was collected slowly, followed by excess of benzene. The remaining benzene was distilled out under reduced pressure and the yellow solids so obtained, were analysed. Their analyses are reported in Table I.

Interchange reactions of diisopropoxy titanium (IV) Schiff base complexes : Slight heat was produced, when the reactants were mixed together in requisite amounts in dry benzene except in the case of 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol. In interchange reactions with phenol and salicylaldehyde, the yellow colour of the reaction mixture changed to red. The reactions were completed by refluxing under fractionation column and the azeotrope and excess of benzene were collected. The resulting compounds were dried under reduced pressure and their analyses with a few characteristics are reported in Tables II and III.

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6. D. C. Bradley and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.